

A MODEL FOR TEACHING STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES**Saxieva Dilfuza Abdinabievna**

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Abstract. *This study provides information on the use of modern pedagogical models in teaching students with disabilities. In modern education, the role of the teacher in providing pedagogical and psychological support to students with disabilities (students with disabilities) is very important. The teacher should organize the teaching method using pedagogical models and based on his/her own pedagogical skills.*

Keywords: *Education, upbringing, pedagogical method, student with disabilities, psychological potential, pedagogical skills, educational model.*

**TA'LIMDA NOGIRONLIGI BO'LGAN O'QUVCHILARNI O'QITISHNING
MODELI**

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda nogironligi bo'lgan o'quvchilarga ta'lim berishda zamonaviy pedagogik modellarini qo'llash haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Zamonaviy ta'limda imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarga (nogironligi bo'lgan o'quvchilar) pedagogik va psixologik yordam ko'rsatishda o'qituvchining roli juda katta. O'qituvchi ta'lim berishda pedagogik modellardan foydalanish orqali va o'z pedagogik mahoratidan kelib chiqqan holda ta'lim metodini tashkillashtirish kerak.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim, tarbiya, pedagogik metod, nogironligi bor o'quvchi, psixologik salohiyat, pedagogik mahorat, ta'lim modeli.*

Introduction

The development of an abnormal child depends on education to a greater extent than that of a normal child. Therefore, if abnormal children are not educated or education begins late, their development is seriously damaged. The formation of mental functions lags behind, the degree of lagging behind normal peers increases, and if the defects are very serious, the

possibilities for mental development may not be realized. The central problem of special didactics is the organization of labor education and upbringing. Its organization in special schools is of particular importance. Consequently, in this process, students are prepared for social life, as well as, to the extent possible, for professional activity, which helps to restore the impaired functions, as well as reduce the level of mental and physical development defects. The upbringing of abnormal children is the main concept of correctional pedagogy, the goal and task of which is to prepare abnormal children for active social life and work, and to form civic qualities in them, using methods and means appropriate to the degree and structure of the defect. The upbringing of abnormal children is carried out on the basis of close communication between the family and the educational institution, mutual support, assistance, demandingness and reasonable kindness. holds. Correctional and educational work as a category consists of a system of measures of general pedagogical influence based on the features of the anomalous development of the individual. In correctional and educational issues, all types and forms of classroom and extracurricular work are used. Correctional and educational work is carried out in the process of educating abnormal children and creates great opportunities for the effective organization of labor education. In the process of labor education, not only professional skills are developed, but also the skills of planning one's own work, the ability to follow oral instructions, a critical assessment of the quality of work and other skills. It is important to create conditions for the communication of abnormal children with normally developed children by correcting their shortcomings. In a number of cases, it is necessary to organize therapeutic corrective measures for anomalous children (therapeutic physical exercises, massage, articulation and respiratory gymnastics, taking medications, etc.). To determine the nature and essence of developmental and behavioral defects in children, to study the causes and conditions of their occurrence. To study the history of the organization and development of correctional and pedagogical activities with children with developmental and behavioral defects. To determine the etymology (causal basis) of socio-pedagogical conditions and psychophysiological development that serve to prevent developmental and behavioral defects in children. To develop technologies, methods and means of corrective and pedagogical influence on children with developmental and behavioral defects. To analyze the content of general and special education of children with developmental and behavioral defects in the conditions of public general secondary education sources. To determine the goals, tasks and main directions of centers for the rehabilitation and protection of children, special institutions. It is necessary to create the necessary educational and methodological

base for the training of teachers organizing correctional and pedagogical activities with abnormal children. Correctional and educational work is a system of special pedagogical measures aimed at eliminating or reducing developmental deficiencies in anomalous children. Correctional educational work is aimed not only at correcting individual defects, but also at their general development. Correction of defects in the development and behavior of students is considered a holistic pedagogical phenomenon aimed at changing the child's forming personality. Correctional and educational activity is a pedagogical action aimed at changing the child's cognitive abilities, improving his emotional-volitional, individual qualities, developing interests and abilities, labor, artistic, aesthetic and other abilities. Correctional developmental education is a differentiated educational system that provides timely qualified assistance to children with disabilities in school and at school, the main task of which is to systematize knowledge aimed at increasing the general level of development of the child, eliminate defects in his development and learning, form insufficiently formed skills and abilities, and correct defects in the child's perception. In working with children with hearing impairment, surdopedagogues are achieving great success. After studying at special evening schools, children of this category of anomalous children successfully graduate from higher educational institutions, and work on an equal footing with everyone else in various enterprises of our country. So, it is possible to eliminate hearing impairments, to fully compensate for them. The main task of educators and teachers is to separate healthy children from children with hearing impairments, to approach them separately, and, if necessary, to ensure that they receive education in special institutions or are involved in integrated education. A student who feels that he cannot express his thoughts orally in special institutions must know how to express himself in writing. To this end, teaching students to express their thoughts orally and in writing is carried out on the basis of the formation of practical speech skills and qualifications. In lessons and classes aimed at developing communicative (oral, written) speech in deaf and hard-of-hearing students, teacher and student activities are organized based on exercises in a specific system, and it is required to be able to adapt all types of didactic tools to the speech process. To ensure the practical mastery of speech materials, situations that create the need for specially created problematic speech (speaking, writing, explaining) are planned in advance. In this case, speech materials are predetermined in the subject curricula, in planning exercises, that is, the correctional pedagogical process is carried out on the basis of a certain system. Speech materials for each lesson are selected and prepared in strict accordance with the principles of the correctional-

communicative system (in accordance with the hearing and pronunciation capabilities of students, with clear pronunciation and easy range of hearing, from simple to complex, from dissimilarity to similarity). The upbringing of the need for colloquial speech begins in the family, that is, extensive conditions are being created for the speech skills and qualifications acquired at school to be strengthened in natural situations in the family and for students to apply them in practice (freely, without fear, without shame). These conditions are created with the participation of family members. The extensive communication and warm attitude of the teacher towards the deaf child is one of the factors that directly affects the child's subsequent education and upbringing and his fate in general. Individualized curriculum - a curriculum that provides for the development of an educational program based on the individualization of its content, taking into account the characteristics and educational needs of a particular student; Inclusive education - ensuring equal access to education for all students, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs and individual capabilities; Adapted educational program - an educational program adapted for the education of people with disabilities, taking into account their psychophysical development characteristics, individual capabilities and, if necessary, ensuring the correction of developmental disorders and social adaptation of these individuals; Special conditions for the education of students with disabilities are conditions for the education, upbringing and development of such students, including the use of special curricula and teaching and upbringing methods, special textbooks, manuals and didactic materials, special technical manuals for collective and individual use, the provision of auxiliary (assistant) services that provide students with the necessary technical assistance, conduct group and individual remedial classes, provide access to the premises of organizations conducting educational activities, and other conditions, without which it may be impossible or difficult for students with disabilities to master educational programs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that teaching students with learning disabilities requires psychological potential and a high level of pedagogical skills from the teacher. The teacher, when applying educational models, teaches the student to develop his/her upbringing, thinking skills, as well as self-control. The main goal of the teacher is to provide education and upbringing to the student with disabilities as much as possible.

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